

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

EVALUATION METHODS IN BUSINESS WRITING ASPECT (ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES FOR ECONOMISTS)

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***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada biznes darslarida, xususan, maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili kurslarida baholash va fikr-mulohaza yuritish usullari o'rganiladi. U turli baholash strategiyalarini, jumladan, biznes o'quvchilari uchun yozish faoliyatini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, u tengdoshlarni baholash va o'z-o'zini baholash kabi innovatsion usullarni muhokama qiladi, ularning o'z-o'zini tartibga soluvchi ta'limga ta'sirini va talabalarning faolligini baholaydi. Umuman olganda, u oliy ta'limda baholash va fikr-mulohaza sifatini oshirish, ta'sirli o'quv muhitini yaratish bo'yicha tushuncha va tavsiyalar beradi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Baholash, tahmin qilish, biznes-klass, ESP (Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili)*

***Annotation.** The article studies assessment and feedback techniques in business classes, especially, in English for Specific Purposes courses. It examines diverse assessment strategies, including writing activities for business learners. Additionally, it discusses innovative techniques such as peer assessment and self-assessment, assessing their impact on self-regulated learning and student engagement. Overall, it provides insights and recommendations to enhance the quality of assessment and feedback in higher education, fostering an impactful learning environment.*

***Key words:** Assessment, evaluation, business class, ESP (English for Specific Purposes).*

It is evident that writing is a complex process activity which demands writers to apply specific skills in the process of producing a piece of text. The type of text we produce can differ from other texts, for example, a paragraph in an essay is totally different from a paragraph in a journal article. It is critical for writers to be aware of writing aspects, style, mechanics, organization, purposes, etc. prior to producing a piece of writing. Here are some types of writing that can be applicable in the EFL/ESL/ESP classroom: Essays or projects

Requesting learners to write essays is an effective method to provide an opportunity to summarize or apply what they have learned during a unit of study. In classrooms with language focus, students have to showcase their ability to use language structures or specific vocabulary in an authentic task. Here is an instance that requires to provide arguments and use the future tense. Students are asked to read articles that state a position or express opinions and conduct mock debates. In the final examination, they produce an argumentative essay in which they stand on the use of mobile phones in the classroom. They should choose for or against, and argue three potential advantages or results using the future tense and the IF, then sentence structure. In their essays, they also incorporate related vocabulary such as

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pro, con, disadvantage, benefit, and drawback. This assignment can also be implemented into the classroom as a project like making a poster or brochure with their positions indicated (Djumabaeva, 1999).

Presentations, speeches, skits, or commercials

Multiple presentations, speeches, skits, or commercial and business-oriented assignments are creative tasks because learners can demonstrate their performative ability what they have learned during learning process in the classroom. These tasks do not require learners to focus on regulations rather encourage creative freedom to perform their ability. Moreover, students prefer to observe their peers act. So, students are much more engaged in attending actively in such activities as well as the presenters who enjoy implementing these assignments. Fulfilling these tasks allow students to perceive and analyze the data as a performer and perceiver which they may not experience by just submitting their essay.

For instance, a summative assessment can be given to students on the same topic of mobile phones where they will have to argue for or against. The same requirements are applied to the task. Commercial or skit with the same requirements can be created (Bus, 2017).

Portfolios

Portfolios include learner’s work used to showcase students’ mastery of subject comprehension. They are: class work, homework, assessment tasks, student peer evaluation.

It is fact that some portfolios aim to demonstrate learner’s performance improvement and student’s understanding of a particular content. For instance, students with less successful assignments can be replaced with more successful assignments. Sometimes instructors request students to describe every item in a portfolio or even reflect about how a piece of work showcases their learning or performance growth. This can be accomplished with any kind of portfolio. Some model questions for learners to answer can be like this:

Narzillaeva, Toshpulatova and Kim listed five types of business documents: business correspondence, employment documents, data description, writing for meetings, and office documents (see Figure 1). They present detailed and constructive information in the course guidebook for both teachers and learners who deliver sessions in Business writing course in educational institutions where English is not the core subject. Each business writing type has its specific features like layout, style, useful phrases, so being aware of these writing genres for business English students is a necessity. Moreover, university teachers need to be good at

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differentiating them, and write properly before teaching to students. Each type of writing contains at least three categories. For example, for employment purposes, students should be able to write CV, and covering letter. Motivation letter can also be added to this type because it is used by students to apply of a scholarship, or a grant.

Minutes

At every business meeting someone is assigned to “take the minutes” (see Sample 4.). This person writes down all important items talked at the meeting and later summarizes what was talked and decided. As a rule, minutes should be delivered within 24 hours to all the attendees and all the people that must be aware of the content. This ensures that individuals stay focused on the issues raised and determine future action points clear in their minds. Minutes are sent to make sure that things discussed at meetings actually get done (Trappe & Tullis, 2006).

Memo

A memo (see Table 6) is a document that you send to people inside the company. The objective of a memo is to get people to do something. In the past, memos were written on paper: now electronic transmission has been widely adopted. To write a good memo you need to plan, organize and edit your ideas carefully. A good memo tells you clearly what you have to do and when you have to do it (Todd, 2002).

Business letter (formal)

Formal business correspondence is usually done by letter (see Sample letter 2) as this leaves a written record which can be kept for reference. Business letters are different with varying objectives: applying for a job, informing people of developments, requesting action, proposing a service, complaining, etc. to write a successful business letter you need to use the appropriate tone and to communicate your message to the reader, using straightforward language” (Trappe & Tullis, 2005, pp.16-17).

E-mail

Email (see Sample Letter 1) is one of the most commonly-used forms of communication in the business world internationally and locally. It is used widely within companies to spread information, requests, results, instructions, recommendations, minutes of meetings, etc. It is an effective, rapid and quite cheap method to communicate with customers and suppliers, both nationally and internationally. Because of the brevity, rapidity, and relative informality of emails, it

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is important to check that all information has been given and that the tone is appropriate (Trappe & Tullis, 2005).

Contract

A document (see Table 12) signed between two parties and it includes information that should be followed by people who sign. The information are about the terms, name and surname of the parties, rules, punishment if a contract is broken by any party. It is usually formal and there are special terms used in a contract such as party, sign, agreement, undertake, terms, etc.

Among the four main sub-skills of English: speaking, listening, reading, and writing, writing is, in fact, the least popular, and not sufficiently studied and most students struggle to learn it. It may seem that writing, in comparison with other types of speech activity, has little didactic potential, so it is extremely important to get an answer to the question: what is the role of writing in the life of modern man and society as a whole without diminishing the significance of the oral form of communication. Writing continues to play an important role in national and interethnic communication. Writing skills in the native and foreign languages are widely demanded.

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